

APPLES AND ITS WATER REQUIREMENTS: SOME WATER RETENTION SUBSTANCES**Botirov Alisher Erkinovich**3rd year PhD studentThe United Graduate School of
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Abstract: Apple is the second high-produced fruit tree in Uzbekistan, and its intensive orchard plantations become vast, and the harvest is top second after grape. At the same time, apple-producing water plays a crucial role, especially in Uzbekistan, with hot and more petite rainfall in summer, lower precipitation in winter. This article reviewed the importance of water, some water-keeping substances for growing apple trees in water resources are under request. Furthermore, this article discussed that water-keeping materials might help farmers grow apple trees under drier weather conditions.

Key words: 'Fuji', 'Marubakaido', 'JM7', 'M.9', Hydretain ES Plus, Menedael, Glutain, Super Sorb C.

Introduction: The economy of Uzbekistan depends heavily on the growing of cash crops; the share of agriculture in the country's GDP is 25.5% (source: www.trade.gov). Traditionally, agricultural production in Uzbekistan has been dominated by cotton and wheat and is less diversified than that of other countries. However, it is gradually moving away from cotton towards the cultivation and marketing of fruits and vegetables and other higher-value crops. Production of fruits such as apples, cherries, and peaches are increasing rapidly, and many new plantations have been established. Intensive high-density orchards were first introduced in the Samarkand region. In 2011, these high-density orchards covered 639 hectares, while in 2015, they increased to 5,817 hectares (Ostonakulov et al., 2016).

Figure-1.1.1. Statistical indicators for seed and drupe fruit production in Uzbekistan during 2017, 2018 and 2019 (thousand tons). Source: *Stat. uz-web site.*

In order to fully and efficiently exploit the export potential of the agricultural sector through increased production and the expansion of the range of fruits and vegetables being grown, two companies, "Uzbekoziqovqatholding" and "UzAgroExport," have taken over the main management tasks as well as the direction of the promotion and the handling of specialized fruit and vegetable exports.

Fruit production has grown rapidly in Uzbekistan over the past five years. Grapes and apples dominate, with apple production coming in second to grapes (Figure-1.1.1.). One of the reasons for this expansion is that it is taking place on land that is being converted from cotton. This expansion of fruit and vegetable production, fruit in particular, because of the initial capital outlays and the time it takes for a grape plantation or orchard to mature, calls for the careful nurturing of the newly planted trees. This is of course holding true for new apple orchards.

Since tree growth and the emergence of healthy branches after planting is vital for early fruiting; careful tree management is necessary for the promotion of tree growth. Uzbekistan has one of the driest climates in Central Asia (Hu Zengyun et al., 2016). Uzbekistan's hot and dry summers puts its apple industry at a disadvantage in the very competitive global apple marketplace. For example, if red-skinned apples are not covered with netting, the fruit will not color well but will instead burn, resulting in faster deterioration. Meanwhile, crop yields are relatively low compared to those in orchards in temperate climates. Finally, modern technologies necessary for the production, storage, sorting, and packaging of apples are costly, since all the equipment has to be imported. Eventually, the amount of rain that falls during the growing season in Uzbekistan is insufficient for commercial apple production and irrigation systems are still under developed.

The availability of branched (feathered) nursery trees and being able to harvest a crop in a tree's second or third year are critical components of high-density apple planting systems (Tojnkó S., and Cmelik Z., 2004). The use of feathered trees combined with large planting widths and minimal pruning can result in significant improvements in the yields of new orchards over the first five years after planting. Higher numbers of feathers at planting result in higher yields in the second and third years (Robinson and Stiles, 1995). As the benefits of highly feathered trees were discovered, it became necessary to develop nursery management techniques to stimulate lateral branch development. In Uzbekistan, however, most nursery trees do not have small branches (feathers). Moreover, young trees do not grow branches after planting under dry conditions. For this reason, promoting branch growth is crucial for early fruit production in this dry growing region.

‘Fuji’ apple tree and relevant rootstocks: The typical domesticated apple is an interspecific hybrid, usually designated as *Malus × Domestica* Borkh (Korban and Skirvin, 1984). The ‘Fuji’ cultivar is a ‘Ralls Janet’ × ‘Delicious’ cross that was bred in 1939 (Smith, 1971; Kikuchi et al., 1997). In 1962, the name ‘Fuji’ was given to the cultivar by researchers at the Horticultural Research Station in Morioka, Japan. The name ‘Fuji’ comes from the town of Fujisaki (Aomori Prefecture, Japan), where the cross was originally made. ‘Fuji’ is one of the best known apples globally, not just in Japan (D.C.FERRE, 2003). ‘Fuji has a long storage and shelf life (7-11 months) and retains its taste and texture (FAO, 2018). There are still problems achieving good coloration. Fruit quality differs, depending on the rootstock and climate, and it tends towards vigorous branch growth (Graham, 1982).

Rootstocks play an important role in sustaining stable tree growth and controlling tree shape in the early fruit-bearing stages of ‘Fuji’ and other young apple trees. Soejima et al. (1998) reported on the benefits of Marubakaido (*Malus prunifolia* Borkh. var. *Ringo* Asami), a semi-vigorous rootstock for apple trees that is widely used in Japan. Major advantages of Marubakaido are its very good anchorage and early and heavy production. Soejima et al. (2010) also studied the dwarfing rootstock JM7 (‘Marubakaido’ × M.9), a rootstock included in the JM series of rootstocks. They found that growth intensity is similar to M.9 and that it is easy to graft by hardwood cutting.

M.9 is currently the most popular dwarfing rootstock used by commercial apple producers in many parts of northern Europe. At maturity, scion trees grown on M.9 are of a size ideally suited to the high-density plantings now favored by many apple growers. “The trees crop precociously and abundantly and, at similar crop loadings, mean fruit size is generally more prominent than that produced by trees on other popular rootstocks, such as MM.106 or M.26” (Webster and Hollands, 1999). Information regarding the different rootstocks gathered during this Ph.D. research are provided in Table 1.1.1.

For the above reasons, M.9 is widely used in modern orchards in Uzbekistan. For growers planning to invest in high-density plantings, rootstock selection alongside effective irrigation practices is essential for healthy young apple tree growth.

Usage of water for intensive orchards: In Uzbekistan, the amount of arable land is limited and the amount of yearly precipitation is low; yearly precipitation is 200-350 mm. Usually, rainfall occurs in late autumn, winter, and early spring, with little or no rainfall from May to October. This amount of moisture is not enough for the production of most crops; therefore, all commercial fruit orchards in Uzbekistan are irrigated. Production areas that do not require irrigation are found only in mountainous areas with yearly precipitation of around 700 mm (Ostonakulov T.E., 2010).

Water is critical to the physiological functioning of an apple tree. Water is the most significant component of the tree by mass, and nearly all growth processes can be inhibited by improper irrigation practices. However, the essential role of water does not mean that water is always scarce. Irrigation as well as the use of ground cover and other ways of managing an orchard's land surface can contribute to the soil moisture necessary for tree vigor and the overall productivity of an apple orchard (Tworkoski T. J., and Glenn D. M., 2008).

After planting, intelligent irrigation practices and the amount of water applied help promote young apple tree growth. Four ways of irrigation are used in fruit orchards in Uzbekistan. These are floor, pool type, flooding and furrow irrigation. Newly planted orchards are irrigated as a norm with 500 m³/hectare, whereas in fruit bearing orchards it is 800-1000 m³/h (Narzieva S., and Ostonakulov T., 2010). According to Aripov (2013), fruit tree water use per hectare is 600-800 m³ in gray soils and 400-450 m³ in rocky soils.

The growing process of young apple trees commences from the lower part of the tree and continues on to the upper part. When they are not being watered directly, the growth of young roots occurs through the intake of water from soil moisture. Therefore, controlling soil moisture levels is vital for growers raising young apple trees.

Soil water retention substances: Sufficient soil moisture and substances used to control the amount and stability of water retention can enhance fruit tree root development and the growth of the upper part of a young tree. There are several soil water retention substances on the market: Hydretain ES Plus (Hydretain, Inc.), a water retention substance that is a blend of organic hygroscopic and humectant components, has been shown to hydrate the soil effectively. Hydretain ES Plus contains sugar alcohols, polysaccharides, and neutral salts of alpha-hydroxy propionic acid. On the other hand, a further study reported that Hydretain ES Plus and other humectants had no observable effect on soil water retention in drought-tolerant coleus ‘Wasabi’ during the plant growth stages (Greenwell et al., 2017).

Super Sorb C is a superabsorbent hydrogel polymer composed of hydrophilic polymers with water retention properties. They can retain water a hundred times their weight. Although these substances were used in the United States as a water-retaining substance in agriculture, they were developed in Japan in the mid-1970s for personal care and hygienic products. (Kabiri et al., 2003).

Menedael is a plant root vitality element, widely used in Japan, that aids root regrowth. Manedael is a vitalizer that improves a plant's health and growth. It can also help to vitalize a weak plant. Menedael is an aqueous suspension that includes iron in the form of ions. The ions are absorbed immediately to help in plant growth. It works by increasing the intake of water and nutrients and stimulates photosynthesis.

Glutain (amino acid “γ-PGA” manufactured by *Bacillus natto*) and Kalpak 66 “ROYAL INDUSTRIES” Co, Ltd (Made in Japan) help retain water in the soil and promote root water absorption.

Conclusion: This article briefly reviewed the ‘Fuji’ apple tree and rootstocks most used in Japan and worldwide, and some water retention substances that might help the growth of apple trees with water resources are limited areas.

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